

PREDICTING MALL EQUITY: A MODERATED MEDIATED MODEL OF MALL IMAGE AND SERVICE QUALITY FROM A VALUE THEORY PERSPECTIVE

Amjad Abu ELSamen

Department of Marketing, College of Business, Zayed University, Abu Dhabi
United Arab Emirates

E-mail: Amjad.abuelsamen@zu.ac.ae
(Corresponding Author)

Saifeddin Al-Imamy

Department of Marketing, College of Business, Zayed University, Abu Dhabi
United Arab Emirates

E-mail: Saifeddin.Al-Imamy@zu.ac.ae

Raed S. Algharabat

Department of Management and Marketing, College of Business and Economics
Qatar University, Qatar

E-mail: ralgharabat@qu.edu.qa

Maytha AL Ali

Department of Management, College of Business, Zayed University, Dubai
United Arab Emirates

E-mail: Maytha.alali@zu.ac.ae

Received: 2021-05-30

Accepted: 2021-09-21

Published online: 2021-10-12

Abstract

This paper empirically tests a moderated mediated model of the effect of hedonic shopping value on the relationship between mall image dimensions and mall equity. The data was collected through a questionnaire from a sample of malls' shoppers in Amman, Jordan. Structural equation model was used to estimate the path relationship in our model. The findings suggest that utilitarian value, awareness, and mall environment all directly affect perceived quality which in turn leads to higher perceptions of mall equity. The findings also support the moderating role of hedonic value on these relationships.

Keywords: mall equity, shopping values, mall image, moderation mediation, emerging market.

Introduction

Retailers rely on brand image to guarantee differentiation in a highly competitive retail market; as it increases customer purchase intention (Erdil 2015; Graciola et al. 2020). To assist mall managers in securing a sustainable competitive advantage, El Hedhli and Chebat (2009) developed shoppers based brand equity (i.e. SBME) measures as a more comprehensive concept compared to the mall image concept that has been used to capture the mall value (El Hedhli & Chebat, 2009). SBME is conceptualized as comprising two components, a) mall awareness, and b) a multidimensional mall image construct consisting of: convenience, mall environment, product and service quality. SBME model is used to explain the process underpinning mall loyalty. Shoppers commitment to a given mall is positively related to their awareness and self-congruency, which is then related to shoppers' evaluation of mall image, specifically, mall environment, product and service quality (Chebat, El Hedhli, & Sirgy, 2009).

In addition to mall image evaluation, other factors pertain to be important to affect customers' response such as shopping perceived value and retail environment (Babin et al.1994; Dennis et al. 2007; El-Adly & Eid, 2015; Huré et al, 2017; Elmashhara & Soares, 2019; S. Kim et al. 2019; Tan, 2019; Picot-Coupey et al, 2020). Hence, both streams of literature on mall image and shopping perceived value successfully explain shoppers' response, but these explanations are in a meal piece fashion and do not take into consideration the expanding domain of customer perceived value concept.

Existing literature incorporated customer perceived value in brand equity models that is concerned only with the perceived value of money, price, or cost, product utility, value endowed by the brand (Aaker, 1996; Abu ELSamen, 2015; Boo, Busser, & Baloglu, 2009; Mackay, 2001; Rajasekar & Nalina, 2008; Shapiro, Reams, & So, 2019). Additionally, existing research in retailing calls for further testing for the role of customer perceived value in generating mall equity. For example, Swoboda *et al.* (2016) found that the importance of retail attributes varies from one sector to another for retail brand equity. The authors recommended examining how perceived value may play a role in affecting the retail brand equity. Moreover, Chebat *et al.* (2009)'s empirical model showed how mall loyalty is moderated by gender, and the authors recommended studying the effect of shopping perceived value as a potential moderator on the mall image and customer loyalty relation. Recently, Graciola et al. (2020) found that both perceived value and brand awareness mediate the relationship between store image and purchase intention. In their research in the Brazilian market, the authors' adopted a multidimensional store image and a unidimensional perceived value definition and recommended expanding the concept of perceived value in future research. Reflecting this, shoppers' positive shopping experience is a key role in the competitive differentiation among the retail industry (Mansori and Chin (2019).

In emerging economy, malls play a pivotal role in consumers' life and they are changing the way consumers like to shop. Middle East offers a great opportunity for mall retailing, and markets in the Middle East continue to attract an increasing number of international retailers, competing with established global retail centers (Koksal, 2019). Further, the Middle East is one of the smallest, yet fast growing regions in the world and it is expected to emerge as one of the world's most competitive landscapes offering value to a worldwide customer base (Prayag & Hosany, 2014). As a result, the traditional shopping behaviour of Arabs has changed as they enjoy shopping from different Western products and brands. (El-Adly, 2007).

Despite the rapid growth in the retail sector, surprisingly, the literature review indicates that only a few studies have been undertaken in the Middle East, despite the region attracting foreign investors and multinational companies (Koksal, 2019; Abu ELSamen and Hiyasat, 2017), and it remains unclear how the characteristics of these malls might affect purchase behaviour (Diallo et al (2018)). Clearly, creating positive brand image and perceived value have its positive effect on purchase intention and brand evaluation (Norfarah et al. 2018; Graciola et al. 2020). However, there is still a need for a better understanding of these complex relationships.

The main aim of this study was to (1) test the hierarchical relationships among mall image dimensions and to test their effect on mall equity using a sample of shoppers from a Middle East context, and (2) to examine the indirect effect of shoppers' perceived value on the relationship between mall image and mall equity. More specifically, this research adds to the existing body of mall shopping by empirically testing a moderated mediated model of the effect of hedonic shopping value on the relationship between mall image dimensions and mall equity.

Literature Review and Hypotheses Development

The awareness-quality effect on customers' attitudes is not straightforward relationship. Previous research asserts that brand awareness is not sufficient to generate high brand equity. Jara and Cliquet (2012) posit that retail brand awareness has indirect effect on brand choice through retail brand image. In hospitality industry, Kayaman and Arsali (2007) assert that the hotel awareness is not sufficient condition for high hotel brand equity, rather, the tangibility, reliability and responsiveness dimensions of perceived quality of hotel service lead to guests' loyalty. Further, Ding and Tesng (2015) found brand awareness/ association enhances customer loyalty through increasing restaurants perceived quality. Similar conclusion is found in mobile communication sector (Balaji, 2011), health care sector (Kumar et al. 2013), hospitality (S. S. Kim et al. 2018), and logistics (Świtała et al. 2018).

To sum up, mall awareness and mall perceived quality are hypothesized to positively influence mall equity (Akroush, Abu-ElSamen, & Jaradat, 2011; Çifci et al., 2016; Diallo, Diop-Sall, Djelassi, & Godefroit-Winkel, 2018; Ding & Tseng, 2015; Londoño, Elms, & Davies, 2016). Additionally, mall awareness is hypothesized to have an indirect positive effect on mall equity through mall perceived quality (Balaji, 2011; Ding & Tseng, 2015; Kumar et al., 2013). Therefore, the current research hypothesizes that:

H₁: Mall perceived quality positively influence mall equity.

H₂: Mall perceived quality mediates the effect of mall awareness on mall equity.

This research posits that mall environment, mall convenience and mall perceived quality leads to higher mall equity. Chebat *et al.* (2009) examined the impact of SBME dimensions on shoppers' loyalty through self-image congruency and commitment to the mall. The authors found that shoppers' commitment to a given mall is positively related to their awareness and self-congruency, which is then related to shoppers' evaluation of mall image, specifically, mall environment, product and service quality.

Swoboda *et al.* (2016) found that when a retailer is easy to shop at, has a comfortable environment along with high service quality and product assortment, the retailer brand equity will increase. Cifci *et al.* (2016) concluded that high service qualities accompanied by lively and interesting presentation are strong predictors of brand equity. In a similar vein, in UAE, El Adly and Eid (2016) found that a convenient mall with recreational environment and attractive interior enhances shoppers' satisfaction and loyalty. Further, Shafiee & Es-Haghi (2017) found mall image and hedonic value, but not utilitarian value, are the main antecedents for shopping well-being.

As such, this research posits that the impact of mall perceived quality can be used as a mechanism to clarify the influence of mall environment and convenience on mall equity. For example, Michon *et al.* (2005) found in a real field experiment that a favourable perception of the retail environment influences product quality perception. Similarly, Haj-Salem, Chebat, Michon, & Oliveira, (2016) found that pleasant mall atmosphere affects customer's perception and loyalty with the mall. Finally, Akroush *et al.* (2011) found that when it is easy to travel to a mall that has a convenient parking, a stimulating and comfortable shopping environment, customers' satisfaction and cognitive evaluation of the mall will increase. Based on the after mentioned discussion, this research hypothesizes that:

H₃: Mall perceived quality mediate the effect of mall convenience on mall equity.

H₄: Mall perceived quality mediate the effect of mall environment on mall equity.

The Moderation Effect of Shopping Hedonic Values

Kim *et al.* (2008) asserted that perceived value of the money mediates the effect of perceived quality dimension of hotel brand equity on revisit intention. Similarly, Pham *et al.* (2016) found that brand equity of quick service restaurants is correlated with revisit intention and this relationship was mediated by perceived value. Ding and Tseng (2015) found that consumers' hedonic emotions from experiencing a fast food brand mediates the effect of that restaurant perceived quality on brand loyalty. In a more recent study, Ruan, Zhang, Liu, & Li (2020) found that customer trust and perceived value of hotels reinforces brand equity.

The link between perceived value and perceived quality has also been examined in different retail categories. For instance, Luk *et al.* (2013) classified retail stores into hedonic and utilitarian categories. The authors found that within hedonic retail categories (i.e. cosmetics, fashion,) shoppers linked perceived service quality with value more than those in utilitarian retail categories (i.e. electronics, supermarkets). The authors recommended assessing the shopping motives for shoppers, rather than simply using stores characteristics as proxy to shopping motives. Toward that end, Doucé and Janssens (2013) examined the effect of shopping environment on shopping intention. The authors assessed shoppers' motives and conclude with no evidence for the impact of pleasant ambient scent and revisit intention for customers with high hedonic shopping motivation in hedonic category retail (i.e. luxury fashion). In another recent study, Konuk, (2018)'s study supported the significant relationship between customer perceived value and perceived quality when considering the purchase of organic private labels in Turkey.

Hence, the utilitarian and aspects of shopping experience clearly plays substantial roles in affecting consumers' evaluation of the brand. Doucé and Janssens (2013) findings however, were influenced by the research context. More specifically, it is unlikely that hedonic shopping motives to moderate the effect of a hedonic shopping stimulus (i.e. pleasant scent) in a hedonic shopping context (i.e. luxury shopping). Moreover, Kesari and Atulkar (2016) assert that both hedonic and utilitarian shopping values positively impact customer satisfaction (Kesari & Atulkar, 2016). This is in-line with recent work that has looked at the hedonic and utilitarian dyad in the hospitality context (Ruan *et al.*, 2020).

Hence, we conclude from previous research (Luk *et al.*, 2013; Doucé and Janssens, 2013) that hedonic motives effect maybe pronounced when evaluating the effect of a utilitarian stimulus. As such, this research posits a moderating effect of hedonic motives when evaluating the effect of a utilitarian stimulus (i.e. convenience) rather than a hedonic stimulus (i.e. mall environment) on a cognitive outcome (i.e. perceived quality). Additionally, because brand awareness enhances customer loyalty through increasing perceived quality (Ding and Tesng, 2015), the awareness-quality

relationship is expected to be higher when shoppers enjoy their shopping experience. Based on the previous reasoning, we hypothesize that:

H₅: The mediation effect of mall convenience, on mall equity through perceived quality is moderated by hedonic shopping values, such that this effect is stronger for customers with high hedonic values.

H₆: The mediation effect of mall environment, on mall equity through perceived quality will not be moderated by hedonic shopping values.

H₇: The mediation effect of mall awareness, on mall equity through perceived quality is moderated by hedonic shopping values, such that this effect is stronger for customers with high hedonic values.

Figure 1 depicts the proposed theoretical model. It proposes that the effects of mall convenience, mall environment and mall awareness on mall equity are mediated by perceived quality, and this mediation is moderated by shopping hedonic values.

Figure 1: Proposed Research Model

Research Methodology

Constructs Operationalization

All research constructs were measured using a multiple-item five-point Likert-type scale run from “Strongly Agree” to “Strongly Disagree”. A list of items measuring the constructs was developed from several sources of available literature, as shown in table 1.

Table 1: Research Constructs and Measurements

Constructs and Items		References
Hedonic Values		Babin <i>et al.</i> , 1994; Akroush <i>et al.</i> , 2011; Kesari and Atulkar, 2016; El Adly and Eid, 2016
HV1	Shopping from (mall name) mall is more than just simply going to the store to purchase what I was looking for	
HV2	Shopping from (mall name) mall creates excitement	
HV3	It was fun being at the (mall name) mall	
HV4	I go to the (mall name) mall for social interaction	
Mall Awareness		El-Hedhli and Chebat, 2008; Abu ELSamen, 2015
MA1	I am aware of the (mall name) mall	
MA2	I can recognize (mall name) mall among other competing malls	
MA3	Some characteristics of (mall name) mall come to my mind quickly	
MA4	When I think of a shopping mall, (mall name) is the first that comes to my mind	
Convenience		El-Hedhli and Chebat, 2008; El Adly and Eid, 2016
CONV1	It is convenient to shop at (mall name)	
CONV2	It is easy to get to the (mall names)	
CONV3	It is easy to park near the (mall name)	
Mall Environment		El-Hedhli and Chebat, 2008
ENV1	The Environment of (mall name) mall lively	
ENV2	The Environment of (mall name) mall is interesting	
ENV3	The Environment of (mall name) mall is cheerful	
Perceived Quality		El-Hedhli and Chebat, 2008
PQ1	(mall name) sells high quality product	
PQ2	Merchandise at this (mall name) is of very good quality	
PQ3	There is a high likelihood that items bought at (mall names) mall will be of extremely high quality	
PQ4	(mall name) mall is known for its excellent services	
PQ5	(mall name) mall provides excellent services to its customers	
Mall Equity		Yoo and Donthu, 2001; Verhoef <i>et al.</i> , 2007
EQ1	I prefer to shop at (mall name) if another is as good	
EQ2	It seems smarter to shop at (mall name) if another is not different	
EQ3	(mall name) mall is well- known	
EQ4	(mall name) mall is unique	

This study was conducted in 5 large shopping malls in Amman, the capital of Jordan using a convenience sample of malls shoppers. We asked individuals to fill in a self-administered questionnaire after their shopping trips. 600 questionnaires were delivered to malls shoppers from which 390 were valid for the analysis.

Findings

The sample shows that Females were twice as much as the males in the research sample and around 70% of the respondents were between the age of 20 and 30 years old. Over 90% of the respondents reported spending at least 1.5 hours in each visit to the mall and 45% of the respondents visited the shopping mall at least once a week.

Next, data was examined for outliers and normality first. As suggested by Hair et al (1998), value of Skewness (-2 to +2) and Kurtosis (-3 to +3) should be within the limit to indicates data normality (Hair et al., 1998). The results show that Skewness value from -1.084 to 0.038 and Kurtosis value ranged from -0.827 to 1.167 indicating that our data is normally distributed.

Measurement Model

First, an exploratory factor analysis (EFA) was employed to Judge Constructs' dimensionality. Results of the pattern matrix revealed six factors in which all items loadings were greater than 0.4 (Table 2), with communalities greater than 0.5 and corrected item to total correlation greater than 0.3 (Brzoska & Razum, 2010). We decided to delete one item (PQ3) due to its weak loading. Second, we conducted a confirmatory factor analysis (Anderson and Gerbing, 1988) using LISREL (8.5) to estimate the measurement model. The model fit indexes meets the cut off points. For instance, CFI were above 0.91, RMSEA were below 0.08, NFI were above 0.80. Table 2 also shows the constructs validity and reliability in the sample. Cronbach alpha and composite reliability values are above or close to 0.70. The average variance extracted (AVE) values are above 0.50, providing support for the convergent validity of (Bagozzi & Yi, 1988). Finally, discriminant validity was confirmed (Table 3) via having AVE's greater than the squared correlation between the two constructs (Fornell & Larcker, 1981).

Table 2: Constructs Reliability and Validity

Constructs	Code	EFA	CFA	ItTC	α	CR	AVE
Hedonic Values	HV1	.768	0.83	.71	0.85	0.86	0.60
	HV2	.816	0.86	.75			
	HV3	.775	0.67	.64			
	HV4	.829	0.74	.71			
Mall Awareness	MA1	.726	0.71	.59	0.77	0.81	0.51
	MA2	.567	0.66	.42			
	MA3	.717	0.73	.63			
	MA4	.750	0.76	.66			
Convenience	CONV1	.699	0.68	.43	0.70	0.74	0.50
	CONV2	.761	0.75	.51			
	CONV3	.563	0.67	.39			
Mall Environment	ENV1	.584	0.67	.57	0.75	0.75	0.51
	ENV2	.504	0.72	.64			
	ENV3	.671	0.73	.53			
Perceived Quality	PQ1	.707	0.74	.57	0.76	0.80	0.50
	PQ2	.705	0.78	.58			
	PQ3	.758	0.72	.57			
	PQ4	.609	0.70	.49			
Mall Equity	EQ1	.519	0.66	.46	0.77	0.82	0.53
	EQ2	.790	0.75	.65			
	EQ3	.691	0.71	.60			
	EQ4	.792	0.71	.59			

Exploratory model fit: KMO 0.882 \geq 0.5

Confirmatory model fit: CFI. 91, GFI.9, REMSA. 06, χ^2 481.24 (194)

FL= EFA loadings \geq 0.5, λ = CFA loadings \geq 0.5, ItTC= Item to Total Correlation \geq 0.3

Table 3. Discriminant Validity

Research Constructs	HV	MA	CONV	ENV	PQ	EQ
HV ($\mu = 3.25$, std = 0.76)	0.60					
MA ($\mu = 3.73$, std = 0.89)	<i>0.16</i>	0.51				
CONV ($\mu = 3.69$, std = 0.67)	<i>0.10</i>	<i>0.09</i>	0.50			
ENV ($\mu = 3.51$, std = 0.74)	<i>0.21</i>	<i>0.36</i>	<i>0.14</i>	0.51		
PQ ($\mu = 3.52$, std = 0.62)	<i>0.13</i>	<i>0.16</i>	<i>0.13</i>	<i>0.25</i>	0.50	
EQ ($\mu = 3.64$, std = 0.56)	<i>0.07</i>	<i>0.17</i>	<i>0.12</i>	<i>0.19</i>	<i>0.25</i>	0.53

Confirmatory model fit: CFI. 91, GFI.9, REMSA. 06, χ^2 481.24 (194). Italics indicates squared correlations between constructs, bold indicates the AVE (≥ 0.5) of the construct

Hypotheses Testing

The Mediating Effect of Perceived Quality

To test H1 to H4, a structural equation model was conducted. An SEM model is estimated in LISREL, where mall convenience, mall environment and mall awareness are the independent constructs, perceived quality the mediator and mall equity is the dependent construct. The fit indexes show adequate model fit ($\chi^2 / df = 336.10/145$), CFI=0.93, NFI=0.88, RMSEA=0.06). The SEM results also indicate that all direct effects are statistically significant. More specifically, perceived quality has a positive relationship with mall equity ($t = 7.34$). Further, mall convenience, mall environment, and mall awareness have a significant relationship with perceived quality ($t = 4.14$, $t = 2.01$, $t = 4.68$), respectively.

Next, we tested the meditational effect of perceived quality on the relationship between the independent constructs and mall equity. To do so, we followed Gerbing and Anderson's (1988) two-step approach: (i) developing a measurement model (CFA) with acceptable fit indexes, and then (ii) running a structural model to test the hypothesized relationships. As results come, the selection between the best fitting models should be conducted via comparing (Hu and Bentler, 1999) fully mediated structural model with and partial mediated structural model. To build the partial mediation model, we added direct paths from each independent variable to mall equity. Results show excellent model fit indexes (χ^2 320.58 /142), CFI = 0.92, RMSEA = 0.06, NFI 0.88). The results from the partial mediation model showed that the additional paths were significant (t CONV = 3.13, t ENVI= 1.99, t MA = 3.68). Furthermore, chi-square difference test (Satorra & Bentler, 2001) was employed to compare full mediation with partial mediation models to govern which one is of better fit to the data. The comparison between the two nested models shows differences in χ^2 of 15.52 > 3.84 (0.05, 3), thus, the results show that the partial mediation model is less parsimonious, thus, supporting H2 to H4.

The Moderation Effect of Hedonic Values

To test the moderation effect of hedonic values, we followed Hayes (2017) method PROCESS module (model 7), a mediated moderated mediated test using the regression boost rapping method in SPSS. The score for each construct was aggregated and the analysis was done on each independent construct, while keeping the other independent constructs covariate (Hayes, 2017). Table 5 shows the effect of mall convenience on mall equity through perceived quality ($a1+a3*w$) *b is significant and positive for higher hedonic values (0.22), and for lower hedonic values (0.11). Furthermore, we find that confidence interval does not cross zero for the difference between these two effects, thus, supporting H5, which means that the mediating impact of perceived quality is stronger for higher hedonic values levels. On the other hand, the impact of mall environment on mall equity through perceived quality is positive and significant for higher hedonic values (0.11), but not for lower hedonic values. We find that confidence interval crosses zero for the difference between these two effects, indicating that the mediational effect does not vary significantly across hedonic values levels, thus, H6 is not supported. Finally, the effect of mall awareness on mall equity through perceived quality is positive and significant for higher hedonic values (0.25), and for lower hedonic values (0.13). Thus, confidence interval does not cross zero for the difference between these two effects, hence, supporting H7.

Table 5: Indirect Effect of Environment, Awareness, Convenience on Equity via Perceived Quality Moderated by Hedonic Values

IV	DV	a1	a3	b	c'	W	(a1+a3*w)*b	CI (L-U)
Mall Convenience	Equity	0.22**	0.14**	0.37**	0.17**	Low HV	0.11*	0.008-0.1
						Hi HV	0.22*	
Mall Environment	Equity	0.14**	0.04	0.41**	0.06*	Low HV	0.04	-0.024-0.05
						Hi HV	0.11*	
Mall Awareness	Equity	0.16**	0.11**	0.35**	0.19**	Low HV	0.13*	0.003-0.08
						Hi HV	0.25*	

Notes:

- Variables were mean centered prior to analysis
- $(a1+a3*w)$ *b: Conditional indirect effect of IV on DV through M at levels of W
- a1= Effect of IV on M
- a3= Effect of Interaction between IV and W on M
- b= Effect of M on DV
- c'= Direct effect of IV on DV
- w= Values of moderators
- CI (L-U) Lower and upper 95% confidence interval within 5000 bootstrap samples for the index of moderated mediated
- *p< 0.05**p<0.01

Results Discussion

Our findings offer evidence of the mediating influence of perceived quality on the effect of mall awareness, convenience and mall environment on mall equity. Moreover, the effect of mall awareness and convenience on perceived quality is moderated by both high and low hedonic values. This suggests that awareness of a mall or convenience to the mall is always related to the perception of quality by its customers. Interestingly, the mall environment affects the perceived quality of the mall but is only moderated by heightened hedonic feelings. This finding helps further our understanding of the experience/shopping dyad within a mall experience as it indicates that shopping malls that wish to be associated with higher perceived quality need to raise awareness of said mall, place it in a convenient location, and make the mall environment one that is consistent with heightened feelings of hedonism. Naturally, hedonism is often been described within the context of the features within a shopping mall environment (Arnold & Reynolds, 2003). As such, this research offers empirical evidence that supports the notion of adding hedonic elements such as comfortable music, appealing store designs and aesthetically pleasing indoor restaurants.

Moreover, the results of the current study as pertaining to convenience and awareness of the mall being moderated by both high and low hedonic value provides a unique contribution and allows mall developers to consider the ratio of utilitarian and hedonic components within a shopping mall e.g. décor vs. stores. As malls are becoming more experiential and hedonic, it still appears that perceived quality is partially determined by the convenience of going to the mall in addition to the hedonic value. This is in contrast to the findings of Sadachar (2014) who argued that malls should provide experiential value rather than utilitarian (Sadachar, 2014). However, our results are consistent with the findings of Muerrilees *et al.* (2016) who advocated a mix of both utilitarian and hedonic elements within shopping malls (Merrilees, 2016; Zhao, 2003).

Finally, with reference to the mediating influence of perceived quality and the moderating role of hedonic value, the findings of this research show a significant association between perceived quality and mall equity. This is consistent with previous findings (Ding and Tseng, 2015; Kumar *et al.*, 2013; Balaji, 2011; Diallo *et al.*, 2018) and suggests that malls that emphasize quality hedonic exchanges with their customers can develop heighten the effect of convenience and awareness of the mall on perceived quality, ultimately elevating mall equity perceptions.

Conclusions, implications, and Future Research

The findings of this research offer contributions that aid mall managers and developers to make informed decisions regarding the experiential and hedonic components of the mall. This study found that utilitarian value, awareness and mall environment all significantly impact customers' perceived quality of the mall. In

addition, this relationship was found to be moderated by hedonic values (both high and low) for awareness and utilitarian value but not for mall environment which provides an understanding of the dynamics between hedonic value, perceived quality and mall environment. Finally, this research found that perceived quality mediates the effect of utilitarian value, awareness, and mall environment on mall equity.

This research provides several implications for theory and practice. The theoretical framework validates the SBME and builds on the shopping value concept by providing empirical data that supports the two concepts. Further, the findings from this research extends the body of literature in shopping mall by examining the complex relationships among shopping perceived values and mall equity in a developing country to respond to a call for further understanding the role shopping mall characteristics in affecting shoppers' response. From a practical perspective, the research findings provide insights that may help developers and mall managers decide on the importance of hedonic elements within their shopping mall. As our findings indicate, having highly hedonic components may improve the mall environment perceptions which leads to heightened perceived value whereas having minimum hedonic elements within the mall could result in negative perceptions of mall environment leading to lower perceived quality.

Our research has several limitations which may be examined in future research. The research was conducted in one geographic location (Amman). Future research could look at expanding the geographic locations and possibly looking at the cultural influence on this model by collecting data from different countries such as Saudi Arabia, the United Arab Emirates, and Egypt to improve our understanding about Middle Eastern consumers. Previous research ascertains the importance of culture as a factor affecting consumers shopping motivation (Prayag and Hosani, 2014), which could moderate the relationship between perceived value and mall equity, as it would be interesting to compare the behavior of Middle Eastern consumers with that of other countries from other parts of the world to investigate the similarities and differences in a cross-cultural study.

Additionally, future research may develop the proposed model by testing other theoretical frameworks. Previous research incorporated different frameworks to examine the relationships between mall environment, satisfaction and loyalty such as theory of planned behaviour, and stimulus-organism-response (SOR) model (Mansori and Chin, 2019). However, the original variables in these frameworks were not tested such as attitude, subjective norms, and behavioral control in the theory of planned behavior, and affect, cognition in SOR model. Future research could incorporate the effect of subjective norms and behavior control as social values and examine how both hedonic values (i.e. affect) and perceived quality (cognition) affects the proposed relationships. Finally, future research could develop clusters of shoppers according to

their motivation and generational cohort as well as examining the effect of socio-psychological variables such as social status.

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